

International research trials that aim to tackle critical global health issues, such as iron deficiency among women, have **greater and lasting impact when they are locally driven and prioritise capacity building amongst the next generation** of researchers and health experts. Effective and accessible training that fosters collaboration and strengthens cross-cultural and -institutional relationships between participating partners and trainees are essential elements for successful trials. To inform training plans suitable to cross-sector/-culture collaboration, we surveyed interest-holders committed to advancing women’s health and developing sustainable solutions to tackle iron deficiency and poor nutrition in Benin and Canada. The **purpose** of this knowledge mobilisation activity is to report insights on factors influencing, and best approaches to conducting, training that meets the needs of participating partners.

Sample	Experts-by-experience: researchers, future trainees, undergraduate and graduate students, NGO project managers, industry partners, and youth & community health advocates
Phenomenon of interest	Insights and perspectives on factors and approaches that influence successful cross-cultural and -sectoral/institutional training of trial team members/trainees
Design	Structured survey informed by academic literature and insights from the Alliance Against Iron Deficiency working group to ensure rigor and relevance of the survey questions
Evaluation	Qualitative thematic analysis of surveys to uncover key themes and practical recommendations
Research type	Qualitative, focused on exploring applied and experiential knowledge of experts-by-experience
Outcome	Inform effective planning of activities that strengthen local capacity in community-based research

Emerging insights

Sustainable trial designs and plans should equip trial team members and trainees to build research and professional skills and to champion the work during the trial and beyond. Successful training requires tailored approaches to be accessible.

Factors influencing equitable participation in training sessions

Barriers

Facilitators

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asynchronous learning: flexible, self-paced options • Role clarity & communication: clear document outlining of trainee roles, and key people to connect with to receive support • Language & communication support: translators, interpreters, and language learning resources 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel & visa support: financial support, subsidies, stipends, and peer support with travel documents and logistics • Language support: peer-to-peer language learning sessions and interpretation at formal trainings 	

Recommended approaches for successful cross-cultural, -sectoral/institutional training

Approaches to best support trainee learning and foster collaboration

Field-based hands-on learning	Knowledge mobilisation/science communications training	Short-term exchange or site visit	Knowledge-sharing seminars across study team members
Collaboration on research projects	Bilateral exchange of trainees from participating institutes	Cross-cultural sensitivity training	

Preferred formats to best support trainee learning and collaboration

Format: Small group virtual workshops	In-person training sessions	Expert-led webinars
Accessible, can occur frequently, and encourages active participation	Beneficial for intensive skill development and fosters deep collaboration	Provides opportunities for learning theoretical content and networking with experts
Benefits:		